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Assessment of Groundwater Geochemistry and Its Suitability for Drinking and Irrigation Practices in the Chakwal District, Punjab, Pakistan

Arifullah^{1,2}, Huang Changsheng^{1,2*}, Nafees Ali^{3,4}, Abdur Rashid⁵, Syed Asim Hussain⁶, Meer Muhammad Sajjad⁷, Oscar Chijioke Nkwazema⁸

¹ Institute of Geological Survey, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan, 388 Lumo Road

² Department of Hydrogeology and Environmental Geology, Wuhan Center of China Geological Survey

³ State Key Laboratory of Geomechanics and Geotechnical Engineering, Institute of Rock and Soil Mechanics, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Wuhan 430071, China

⁴ University of Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing 100049, China

⁵ School of environmental studies, China University of Geosciences, Wuhan

⁶ University of Baltistan, Skardu, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan

⁷ University of Chinese Academy of Sciences (UCAS), Beijing 101408, China

⁸ School of Mechanical Engineering and Electronic Information, China University of Geosciences Wuhan, 388 Lumo Road

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ABSTRACT

Groundwater is considered a potential water source for both human use and irrigation. It contributes to the sustainability of semi-arid and arid zones around the globe. Pakistan is enlisted in the world's lack of access to safe potable water. In the Chakwal district, groundwater quality has deteriorated during the last few decades due to climatic changes and anthropogenic sources. Therefore, 123 groundwater samples were examined for the presence of trace elements and significant ions to examine the water's acceptability for human consumption and agricultural usage. The Gibbs plot demonstrated that rock dominance and precipitation are the primary controlling processes governing groundwater chemistry. The Piper plot identified three water types in the research area: calcium type, chloride type, and no dominant type.

Furthermore, the water quality index (WQI) was performed to evaluate the quality of the water for human consumption. The results showed that 85% of the water samples were poor for human consumption. The pH extended from 7.1 to 8.8, implying the aquifer's

slightly alkaline water. Irrigation water techniques such as sodium percentage (Na %) and Kelly ratio (KR) show that most water samples are susceptible to salinity. The Na/Cl plot shows the enrichment of Na⁺ in the groundwater acquired mainly from the weathering of silicates. The chloro-alkaline indices revealed that direct and reverse ion exchange processes were also involved in the evolution of hydrochemistry in the aquifer. Geogenic and anthropogenic activities are deteriorating the groundwater quality of the Chakwal district. To sustain groundwater quality, critical policies are indispensable and must be constructed.

Keywords

Groundwater Quality, Water Quality Index, Hydrochemical Modeling, Statistical Analysis, Irrigation Water Quality, Chakwal District.

Introduction

Groundwater is a vital freshwater supply for the public, industry, agriculture, and diverse rural communities worldwide. Compared to surface water, groundwater is safer from pollutants because pollution is less when it filters through the soil (Ansa-Asare, Darko, & Asante, 2009). Nevertheless, the aquifer's quality is deteriorating because of the contamination and overexploitation caused by the rising population. Pollution can come from geogenic (naturally occurring chemical elements) and different anthropogenic activities. Groundwater quality data can reveal the depositional environment of the rocks and the aquifer's inflow, outflow, mobility, and preservation (Prasanth, Magesh, Jitheshlall, Chandrasekar, & Gangadhar, 2012; Walton, 1970). In many regions of the globe, the need for clean water is rising due to fast population growth, modernization, industry, and heavy farming movements (Raju, Shukla, & Ram, 2011; Reddy, Sunitha, Prasad, Reddy, & Reddy, 2019). Drinking and agriculture are the primary groundwater used in many developing countries, such as Pakistan. Increasing the dependency on groundwater resources, which are considered safer than water bodies on the earth's surface, has resulted in an over-reliance on and, in some cases, an over-use of the water resource (Abbas et al., 2018). According to a report Asian report (Asia, 2000), 30% of diseases in Pakistan are related to low water quality, including diarrhoea in children, a common water-borne illness. Drinking water must be treated to remove disease-causing toxic chemicals and odour-producing compounds and make it appropriate for ingestion and other domestic uses. The quality of water used regularly is directly related to human health. According to the recommendations of numerous health organizations, groundwater in some areas of Pakistan does not meet the quality standards required for human ingestion (Raza, Hussain, Lee, Shakoor, & Kwon, 2017; Siyal, Ahmed, Samo, Samo, & Pathan, 2020). The district has 1.49 million people, with 81% living in rural parts (STATISTICS, 2007). Using the study area's groundwater is vital to meet the continuously increasing drinking and agricultural supply demands. As the study area is located in Pakistan's semi-arid zone, the resource provides nearly the primary source of economic development. There are several dug wells in the region during the rainy season where water is stored (Afzal, Yaseen, Mahmood, & Khan, 2015). Previous studies in the research area focused on the aquifer recharge system, which found nitrate contamination in some parts of Chakwal (Tahir & Rasheed, 2008). Still, the studies did not detail the distribution pattern of groundwater standards for human

consumption and cultivation throughout the district. The current study examined the aquifer's water quality used for domestic and agricultural purposes. The outcome will give a baseline on groundwater standards in the Chakwal district and discern the causes of groundwater contamination and its monitoring.

Materials and methods

1.1 Study Area

The Chakwal district is in Pakistan's Punjab province, on the Pothohar Plateau. It is a rain-forested district between latitude 33° 01'21"N and longitude 72 45 49 "E (Figure 1). The Provisional Census Report (2017) estimates that the district's total population is 1.49 million, and it has a covered land area of 1,652,441 acres. Climatically, the Chakwal district lies within the semi-arid zone. The coldest month of the year is December. The warmest is in June, with a range of summer temperatures of 15 to 40 degrees Celsius, with winter temperatures ranging from 4 to 25 degrees Celsius. The district receives an average yearly rainfall of 558 to 625 millimetres. 70% of the yearly rainfall comes during the monsoon season, extending from June to September (Siddiqui, Safi, Tariq, Rehman, & Haider, 2020). It has a diverse terrain that ranges from relatively flat ground to undulating landscapes with exposed rocks to heavily degraded areas with enormous, complex gullies and cuts, many seasonal streams and small dams (Ghani, Arshad, Shabbir, Mehmood, & Ahmad, 2013).

Furthermore, the district has various tourist destinations, and fascinating landscapes, like Uchali, Khabar, and Kallar Kahar. The vegetation consists mainly of grasses and light broadleaved scrub. Agriculture is heavily reliant on rain and is vulnerable to drought if there is not enough. Only 8% of the farmland is aerated through tube wells, canals, and wells. Wheat is the main crop farmed in the area, but maize, peanuts, garbanzo beans, durra, millet, and soya beans are grown in small spots (Balouch, Rais, Hussain, & Akram, 2016). Water scarcity and soil erosion are currently plaguing the area, posing a severe danger to crop output. Therefore, soil erosion leads to increased water runoff, nutrient depletion, and nutrient deficiency, leading to decreased crop yields (Moyo, 2003). In the Chakwal area, there is no extensive irrigation system. There are several storm channels, most of which are active during the rainy season. Because the Chakwal region is a barani area, groundwater resources must be developed to meet agricultural and domestic water needs (Afzal et al., 2015).

Fig.1 Geographical map of the study with sample locations.

1.1.1 Regional Geology and Hydrogeology

The Chakwal district is situated at the start of the eastern Salt Range and the Pothohar plateau. The rock formations exposed in the Pothohar area range from the Pre-Cambrian to the Quaternary. Thrusts and associated salt diapirism in the Salt Range area bring to the surface layers containing Precambrian evaporates. A sedimentary succession encompassing Permian to Middle Cretaceous, Cambrian, Neogene, and Paleogene strata covers the Precambrian rocks in the region (Baker et al., 1988). Eocene limestone evaporates, and red beds; Pleistocene-Miocene sediments of river and terrace gravel and loam, Holocene alluvial deposits are deposited on the Pothohar Plateau and adjacent Kohat Plateau (Elahi & Martin, 1961). The salt range has extensive deposits of rock salt. In the eastern part of this formation, the Lower Permian rocks are made of mudstone, siltstone, sandstone, and conglomerate formed when Gondwana was covered by ice (Wynne, 1881).

The predominant soil types in the Chakwal district are the fine-grained sandy loam, and sandy clay loam types. The subsoil comprises cohesive soil, gravel, and fractured rock debris. No alluvial deposits exist except for a few narrow strips formed due to the continuous flow of natural hill streams. As a result, there is no substantial aquifer in the subsoil that is refilled by precipitation and begins to dry up due to frequent pumping in the subsurface. Because of the rolling landscape of the city, the water table depth ranges between 70 and 100 feet. The majority of the water in the subsoil is saline, with TDS levels ranging from

800 to 2000 ppm. The depth of different water pumps installed in the city ranges from 100 to 150 ft. The soils of the alluvial terraces and fragmented ancient loess area have silt loam and silt texture, with pH levels ranging from 7 to 9. The area's climate, geology, and evapotranspiration play a significant role in groundwater recharge. The average recharge potential projected was 60% of the rain of 148mm (Afzal et al., 2015).

1.2 Sampling and Analytical Analysis

In total, 123 groundwater samples have been taken from various places around the district of Chakwal, as illustrated in Figure 1. Pre-cleaned polyethene bottles were used to collect samples from tube wells, opened bores, dug wells, and hand pumps. Before sampling, the water was cleaned for 5–10 minutes to remove stagnant water. Basic water quality parameters like temperature, pH, electrical conductivity (EC), and total dissolved solids (TDS) were measured during sample collection. The samples were then moved to the Pakistan Centre of Research in Water Resources (PCRWR) laboratory for additional analysis. A pH meter and an electrochemical tester were used (Hac 44600-00, Loveland, CO, USA) (TDS). Major anions, such as NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} were measured using an ultraviolet-visible (UV-VIS) spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena, Jena, Germany). In contrast, chloride and bicarbonates were determined using a dilution technique (Analytik Jena, Jena, Germany) (Association, Association, Federation, & Federation, 1912). Analyses of Fe^{2+} , K^+ , and Na^+ were conducted using a flame photometer (PFP7, Cambridgeshire, UK). Using volumetric titration with ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA, 0.05 N), Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were detected with a 2% analytical error. Acid titration with methyl orange was used to determine the total hardness of the samples. An atomic emission spectrophotometer (AAS Vario 6 Analytik Jena, Jena, Germany) was used to look for arsenic in the soil.

1.3 Groundwater type and Classification

Geochemical models like the Piper linear diagram and Gibb's plot were developed to investigate the research area's dominant hydrochemical facies and quality-control processes. The Piper diagram was prepared using Grapher software, whereas Gibb's plot was prepared using Microsoft Excel by plotting the anions $\text{Cl}^-/\text{Cl}^- + \text{HCO}_3^-$ and the cations $\text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+ / \text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+ + \text{Ca}^{2+}$ against TDS, respectively.

1.4 Ion Exchange Processes and Mineral Phase

The Indices of Chloro-Alkaline (CAI-I and CAI-II) were calculated to explain the base interchange reaction mechanism. To compute the Chloro-Alkaline Indices, we used the following formulas:

$$\text{CAI} - 1 = \frac{\text{Cl}^-(\text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+)}{\text{Cl}^-} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{CAI} - 2 = \frac{\text{Cl}^-(\text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+)}{\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{SO}_4^{2-} + \text{CO}_3^{2-} + \text{NO}_3^-} \quad (2)$$

Estimating geochemical activities in subsurface water is often explained using saturation indices, which rely on the imbalance between mineral water phases and aqueous (Ndoye, Fontaine, Gaye, & Razack, 2018).

In Hydrogeochemical research, the saturation index (SI) is an extensively used indicator. PHREEQC North American Academic Research, 5(4) | April 2022 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6499073> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 148

(Parkhurst & Appelo, 1999) has been used to determine the SI of several key minerals, like gypsum, dolomite, fluorite, calcite, and Halite. The SI was calculated with the help of the equation given:

$$(SI = \log \frac{IAP}{Ks(T)}) \quad (3)$$

IAP denotes the solution's ion behaviour component, and KS (T) represents the reaction's equilibrium constant at temperature T. This analysis considers the mineral saturation if the SI value is below 0. It is assumed to be oversaturation if the SI value is greater than 0, while the SI value at 0 means the state of equilibrium.

1.5 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical method for determining the relationship between two variables. We used Pearson's correlation analysis to determine the relationship between numerous water chemical parameters in our study area.

1.6 Silicate Weathering

Employing Origin.2021 software, multiple bivariate scatter plots were constructed to categorize the silicate weathering, carbonate weathering, and evaporation processes in groundwater samples from the research area.

1.7 Water Quality Index (WQI)

The WQI index has been employed to determine the drinking water quality using a weighted arithmetic index (Brown, McClelland, Deininger, & O'Connor, 1972). The subsequent steps were used to figure out the WQI.

Step 1: Calculated the unit weight (W_n) factors for each sample by using the formula

$$W_n = \frac{K}{S_n} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Where, } K = \frac{1}{1/S_1} + \frac{1}{1/S_2} + \frac{1}{1/S_3} + \frac{1}{sn} = \frac{1}{\sum \frac{1}{sm}} \quad (5)$$

S_n = standard desirable value of nth parameters.

W_n = 1 (unity).

K = constant for proportionality.

Step 2: Calculated the sub-index (Q_n) value by applying the formula

$$Q_n = \frac{[(V_n - V_o)]}{[(S_n - V_o)]} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Where,

V_n = mean concentration of the nth parameter.

S_n = standard desirable value of the nth parameter.

V_o = actual values of the parameters in water (generally V_o = 0) for maximum variables apart from pH.

$$QpH = \frac{[(VpH-7)]}{[(8.5-7)]} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Step 3: combined step 1 & step 2

$$\text{Overall WQI} = \frac{\sum WQn}{\sum Wn} \quad (8)$$

1.8 Irrigation Water Assessment

The sodium percentage (Na %), sodium absorption ratio (SAR), permeability index (PI), and Kelly's ratio (KR) have been deployed to assess the feasibility of water for agriculture. In addition, Wilcox (Wilcox, 1955) and USSL diagram (Staff, 1954) were also plotted to explain the sodium and salinity hazards based on calculated values of sodium percentage and sodium absorption ratio.

The following formulas were used to find the SAR and Na%, PI, and KR.

$$SAR = \frac{Na^+}{\sqrt{\frac{Ca^{2+}+Mg^{2+}}{2}}} \quad (9)$$

$$Na\% = \frac{Na^+}{Na^++K^++Ca^{2+}+Mg^{2+}} \times 100 \quad (10)$$

$$KR = \frac{Na^+}{Ca^{2+}+Mg^{2+}} \quad (11)$$

$$PI = \frac{Na^++\sqrt{HCO_3^-}}{Ca^{2+}+Mg^{2+}+Na^+} \times 100 \quad (12)$$

Result and Discussion

2.1 Groundwater Hydrochemistry

The groundwater's physico-chemical variables were statistically examined to identify their physicochemical characteristics: this analysis measured pH, TDS, EC, and major anions and cations of the water samples. The analyzed chemical parameters were then compared with the World Health Organization (WHO) standard. Each variable's maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviation are listed in Table 1. The pH varied from 7.1 to 8.8, having a mean of 7.8, signifying that the water in our research area is slightly alkaline. The pH is considered safe between 6.5 and 8.5 (Rao, 2006). Only two of the 124 water samples showed pH levels above the WHO's acceptable range. Water's electrical conductivity (EC) is the most important factor in assessing whether it is safe to drink and use for irrigation (Jamali, Solangi, & Keerio, 2020). The EC extended from 98.2 to 7059 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ showing a mean value of 1780.1. EC revealed that 103 water samples crossed the WHO limit of 1000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, while the remaining showed that the EC was within the allowable range. Total dissolved solids (TDS) parameters are commonly used to measure water savoury (Chen et al., 2019). According to (Adelekan & Ogunde, 2012; Kim, Susaya, Park, Uhm, & Hur, 2013), water with high TDS would make water saltier and causes gastrointestinal exasperation while low TDS has no harmful impact on public health.

Table 1 Quantitative assessment of physico-chemical parameters of the aquifer samples.

Chemical parameters	W.H.O standards	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation	Samples E.P.L	Samples E.P.L (%)
pH	6.5-8.5	7.1	8.8	7.8	0.27	2	2%
EC (μ S)	<1000	98.2	7059	1780.1	1188.78	103	83%
TDS (mg/L)	<1000	16	6414	1043.3	781.26	46	37%
Hardness (mg/L)	100-500	70	1680	296.3	228.13	8	7%
HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	150-300	200	995	411.1	132.29	109	89%
Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	75	8	1200	67	120.91	21	17%
F ⁻ (mg/L)	0.6-1.5	0.08	2.99	0.6	0.39	7	6%
Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	30-150	5	182	40.3	30.32	2	2%
Na ⁺ (mg/L)	50-200	50	950	259.8	144.24	79	64%
K ⁺ (mg/L)	30-200	0.2	51	2.84	5.76	Nil	Nil
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	250	14	1817	202.7	242.15	25	20%
NO ₃ (N)	45	0.01	270	13.3	36.49	7	6%
PO ₄ (mg/L)	0.1	0.01	9	0.10	0.08	44	35%
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	250	0.5	1319	167.1	191.48	12	24%
Fe (mg/L)	1.5	0.01	2.62	0.28	0.38	2	2%
As (ppb)	10	0	13	0.87	1.59	1	0%
Turbidity(NTU)	<5	0.01	38	3.55	7.49	12	10%

E.P.L = exceeding permissible limit

TDS varied between 16 and 6414 mg/L, with a median of 1043.3 mg/L. 37% of the samples showed high TDS concentration. TDS levels of less than 1000 mg/L are considered safe (WHO., Organization, & Staff, 2004). Furthermore, minerals, soluble salt dissolution, and shallow groundwater evaporation can increase salinity (Qureshi, Lashari, Kori, & Lashari, 2011). The research area mostly consists of agricultural land, so that the high TDS concentration might be due to agricultural activities. The K⁺ and Na⁺ concentrations were extended from 50 to 950 mg/L and 0.2 to 51 mg/L, with a mean of 259.8 mg/L and 2.84 mg/L. All water samples exhibited permissible K⁺ concentrations; however, the sodium concentration in 79 samples was significantly higher than the prescribed range. High sodium amounts in groundwater are due to the decomposition of sodium-containing minerals and the rising of the water table. Dissolved solids remain after evaporation and accumulate over time after multiple water irrigations. These stored ions leach down to the groundwater (Van Weert, Van der Gun, & Reckman, 2009). The Mg²⁺ and Ca²⁺ concentrations extended from 8 to 1200 mg/L and 5 to 182 mg/L, showing a median of 67 mg/L and 40.3 mg/L sequentially. Contact with carbonate rocks results in high Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ concentrations. HCO₃⁻ and Cl⁻ from 200 to 995 mg/L and 14 to 1817 mg/L, sequentially. 109 HCO₃⁻ and 25 Cl⁻ samples have high concentrations that exceed the WHO's recommended limit due to the disintegration of Halite, gypsum, and sulfate-bearing minerals. (Wu et al., 2017). Furthermore, anion concentrations are presented in order of their abundance HCO₃⁻ > PO₄³⁻ > Cl⁻ > SO₄²⁻. Minimum and maximum concentrations of bicarbonate, phosphate, chloride and sulphate are ranging from 200 to 995 mg/L, 0.01 to 9 mg/L, 14 to 1817 mg/L and 0.5 to 1319 mg/L with averages from 411.1 mg/L, 0.10 mg/L, 202.7 mg/L and 167.1 mg/L respectively (Table 1). 109 samples of HCO₃⁻ are beyond the WHO permissible limit of 300mg/L, whereas 25 samples showed high Cl⁻ concentrations. Chloride is a chemical element that is relatively stable in water. Weathering, the leaking of

sedimentary rock and soil, and the discharge of local sewage are all potential sources of chloride pollution (Prasanth et al., 2012). The sulfate permitted range in potable water is 250mg/L. Our 24% samples have sulfate concentrations higher than the WHO's recommended guidelines. Low sulfate levels in the groundwater indicate that there may be few industries in the study area, whereas high sulfate suggests human supplies and industrial operations (Mostafa, Uddin, & Haque, 2017). Following WHO recommendations, fluoride in drinking water should not exceed 1.5 mg per litre. Seven water samples with high fluoride contaminations have been found in the study area. The average pH value of high Fluoride concentration samples is 7.9. An alkaline environment provides favourable conditions to accumulate F^- in groundwater (Chen, Qian, Wu, Gao, & Li, 2017). It contributes to disintegrating the F^- bearing minerals. Other resources of high F^- concentrations in groundwater are agricultural activities and ceramic industries' waste water. Arsenic and nitrate concentrations extended from 0.01 to 270 mg/L and 0 to 13 ppb, with a median of 13.3 mg/L and 0.87 ppb, respectively. Except for one sample, none of the samples were contaminated with arsenic. The WHO has established a standard limit of 45 mg/L for NO_3^- . Seven samples revealed elevated nitrate levels in our water samples. Siphoning from inappropriate disposal of livestock manure and the widespread use of chemical fertilizers, the nitrate content in groundwater in agricultural areas has risen dramatically in recent decades (Karthikeyan, Rajendran, Ramasamy, & Lakshmanan, 2012; Mostaza-Colado, Carreño-Conde, Rasines-Ladero, & Iepure, 2018).

2.2 Hydrogeochemical Facies

A Piper plot is generally used to define the hydrochemistry based on ions concentration (Piper, 1944). In this plot, cations and anions were plotted to depict sample grouping and predict hydrochemical facies from samples or groups of samples (Figure 2).

The cations and anions define the abundance of each component as a percentage of their total sum (meq %). According to the piper plot, groundwater in the research area is primarily CaCl type and no dominant type, while sodium-type and mixed CaMgCl-type water can also be found in some parts of the research area.

Fig.2 Piper diagram illustrates the evolution of Hydrochemical facies and the groundwater type in the study area.

In the cation section, most samples come from the calcium type zone, while a few samples show the prevalence of the sodium type. Calcium levels in groundwater could be related to both geological and anthropogenic processes. There are two ways that calcium can get into groundwater: fertilizer in farming and acid rain that breaks down limestone and dolomite (Ganyaglo et al., 2010). The chloride water type is found in many samples throughout the anion section, with no dominant type. Chloride in groundwater indicates anthropogenic activity such as sewage leakage and irrigation land water (Bhatia, 2003).

2.3 Mechanism Controlling the Geochemistry of Subsurface Water

Various hydro-geochemical methods, like evaporation, precipitation, and rock-water interaction, could be investigated using the Gibbs plot. The relationship between hydrochemistry and subsurface geology influences groundwater quality and can help anticipate water genesis (Gibbs, 1970). The Gibbs diagram was plotted separately with the proportion of major anions and cations against TDS (Figure 3). The majority of anions' samples come from the rock dominance zone. Only a few samples showed precipitation and evaporation, implying that fluid-rock interaction mainly influenced groundwater chemistry in the research area. The cations plot showed that only a few samples were in the rock and evaporation dominance zones, while most samples were outside the plot preview. According to (Mattos, Cruz, De Paula, & Sales, 2018; Vickers, 2017), this phenomenon could be related to anthropogenic contamination. Even though the impact of urbanization does not have a perfect mark in this way of evaluation, it is thought that the original Gibbs framework suggests that the effects of human activities on water chemistry are relatively weak.

Fig. 3 Gibbs plot shows the ion concentration of the groundwater samples.

2.4 Major Ions Provenance and Hydrogeochemical Evolution

2.4.1 Correlation Analysis

Correlation Analysis is a frequently deployed statistical technique for determining the correlations between two variables. In this study, we applied Spearman's correlation matrix to understand the correlations of major ions. Table 2 illustrates the correlation between the predominant ions. In correlation analysis, a positive correlation between two variables indicates that they originate from the same source, whereas a negative correlation indicates that they originate from distinct sources. On the basis of Spearman's correlation matrix, EC shows strong correlation with TDS (0.78), Na^+ (0.70), Cl^- (0.82), and moderate correlation with SO_4^{2-} (0.67), and NO_3^- (0.69). TDS has a strong relationship with Na^+ (0.72) and Cl^- (0.92). Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} have considerable negative correlations with pH ($r=0.42$, and $r=-0.43$), implying that a low pH value enhances Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} occurrence. Calcium and magnesium have a weak correlation, suggesting that dolomite is not the source of both. This is based on the negative correlation between HCO_3^- and Mg^{2+} . Also, Cl^- and Na^+ usually go together if they come from the Halite's weathering. However, cation exchange and weathering of silicates could also impact their interaction (Nagaraju, Thejaswi, & Sreedhar, 2016). In addition, if Na^+ and Cl^- are positively correlated, their sources are the same in maximum samples. On the other hand, they have a strong negative correlation with SO_4 , Cl^- , and NO_3^- , which means they come from different sources. In the same way, the dissolution of Halite and chloride salt is shown by a positive correlation between Na^+ and Cl^- (0.73), which leads to a similar concentration of the aqueous solution.

Table 2 Pearson's correlations of groundwater parameters.

Parameters	pH	EC	TDS	Ca ²⁺	Mg ²⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺	HCO ₃ ⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ⁻	F ⁻	Hardness
pH	1													
EC	-0.31	1												
TDS	-0.43	0.79	1											
Ca ²⁺	-0.42	0.60	0.78	1										
Mg ²⁺	-0.43	0.54	0.59	0.53	1									
Na ⁺	-0.18	0.70	0.73	0.36	0.37	1								
K ⁺	-0.16	0.15	0.12	0.08	0.25	0.10	1							
HCO ₃ ⁻	-0.12	0.10	0.03	-0.12	-0.09	0.30	-0.06	1						
Cl ⁻	-0.38	0.82	0.92	0.82	0.66	0.73	0.20	-0.11	1					
SO ₄ ²⁻	-0.30	0.66	0.80	0.66	0.65	0.68	0.15	-0.17	0.83	1				
NO ₃ ⁻	-0.32	0.68	0.75	0.79	0.61	0.41	0.03	-0.20	0.78	0.58	1			
PO ₄ ⁻	-0.11	-0.09	-0.06	-0.09	-0.03	-0.03	-0.11	0.10	-0.10	-0.08	-0.07	1		
F ⁻	0.06	0.01	0.00	-0.17	-0.16	0.22	0.02	0.17	-0.01	0.01	-0.23	0.13	1	
Hardness	-0.48	0.46	0.54	0.47	0.69	0.27	0.21	-0.01	0.56	0.37	0.46	-0.07	-0.13	1

2.4.2 Weathering and Dissolution

Silicate weathering influences groundwater's major ions (Subramani, Rajmohan, & Elango, 2010). The characteristics of silicate weathering are complex because of the irreconcilable structure of disintegration of silicate, which produces a range of solid phases (mainly clay) with various dissolved minerals (Saravanan, Srinivasamoorthy, Gopinath, Prakash, & Suma, 2016). Na⁺ enrichment in groundwater samples is presented in (Figure 4a). Na⁺ is the predominant cation formed during rock weathering and halite dissolution in the research area. If sodium is obtained only from Halite in groundwater, the ratio of Na/Cl must be equal to 1.

In contrast, a ratio greater than or equal to 1 indicates that Na⁺ could be derived from silicate weathering and ion exchange. A proportion more than or equivalent to 1, meaning the silicate weathering and ion-exchange processes. The scatter (Figure 4a) depicts that most samples are along and above the 1:1 line. Demonstrating that Na⁺ in the subsurface water could cause halite dissolution and weathering of Na-rich minerals and ion exchange. Clay minerals are sources of high Na⁺ in the groundwater, like sodium aluminium, albite aluminium, or silicate sodium montmorillonite (Feng et al., 2020).

The excess sodium ions in groundwater may result from ion exchange processes and silicate weathering (Kumar, Ramanathan, Rao, & Kumar, 2006). (Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺) Versus (HCO₃⁻ + SO₄²⁻) scatter diagram has been plotted to illustrate whether the ions come from silicate or carbonate weathering. Figure 4b depicts that a large percentage of the samples fell under the aquiline.

Fig.4 Scatter Plots of Na⁺ /Cl (a), Ca²⁺+ Mg²⁺/SO₄+HCO₃ (b), and (c) (Ca²⁺ + Mg²⁺ - (SO₄-HCO₃) / (Na+ Cl) (meq/L).

It shows that silicate weathering is the leading procedure for enriching Ca⁺ ions in groundwater. Gypsum dissolution might cause calcium and sulfate concentrations in subsurface water. It can be expressed as

Samples within the aquiline imply that they were formed through the absorption of gypsum or anhydrite, whereas the prevalence of SO_4^- over Ca^+ indicates that calcium is precipitated from calcite. Figure 5c depicts that most samples show an excess of sulfate over calcium, whereas few samples fall along the aquiline. Furthermore, the $(\text{Na}^+ + \text{K})/\text{TZ}^+$ indicator was used to analyze the cation supply to groundwater through silicate weathering. According to (Stallard & Edmond, 1983), samples lying over 0.5 TZ^+ aquiline are considered a low silicate weathering process. In contrast, a trend to $\text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+ = \text{TZ}^+$ line represents the prevalence of silicate weathering that provides cations, predominantly potassium and sodium, in the groundwater. The scatter plot (Figure 5a) exhibits that few samples are falling above the 0.5 TZ^+ , while most samples are along the aquiline 0.5 TZ^+ and trend to $\text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+ = \text{TZ}^+$ line, which suggests the existence of silicate weathering in the groundwater. The $\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+} / (\text{TZ}^+)$ plot is also a graphical method to determine the silicate weathering. Suppose the samples have a linear relationship with the line 1:1 ($\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+} = \text{TZ}^+$). In that case, it indicates a high concentration of Ca and Mg-rich minerals due to silicate weathering. In contrast, if the water samples are above the ($\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+} = \text{TZ}^+$) line, it indicates less silicate weathering (Sonkamble, Sahya, Mondal, & Harikumar, 2012). Figure 5b explains that multiple samples over the 0.5 TZ^+ line indicate low silicate weathering, only a few samples aligned with the 1:1 aquiline, implying the involvement of other geochemical mechanisms.

Fig.5 (a) Bivariate plots of (Na + K) versus Total Cations. (b): The Ca+Mg/total Cations (TZ^+) Bivariate Plot. (c): Scatter plot of Ca versus SO_4 .

The bivariate plot of Na^+ -normalized Ca^{2+} vs Na^+ -normalized Mg^{2+} and Na^+ -normalized Ca^{2+} vs HCO_3^- investigates the relative influence of three main weathering processes (carbonate, silicate, and evaporation) on groundwater ions concentration (Mukherjee & Fryar, 2008). Na^+ -normalized Ca^{2+} vs Mg^{2+} plot (Figure 6a) illustrates the chemistry of aquifer affected mainly by silicate weathering and evaporation dissolution. However, some samples were placed between the later carbonate and silicate weathering. Furthermore, the Na^+ normalized Ca^{2+} vs HCO_3^- plot (Figure 6b) depicts the absence of carbonate dissolution as most samples lie close to silicate weathering and in the middle of evaporation and silicate weathering zone. Similarly, $(Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}) - (SO_4^{2-} + HCO_3^-) / (Na^+ + K^+ - Cl^-)$ (meq/L) plot is extensively used to examine the influence

of ion exchange in groundwater samples. Negative values are typically used to represent cation exchange, which causes ions to accumulate on the top in fine-grained aquifer materials to be exchanged by ions in solutions (Ettazarini, 2005).

Fig.6 Bivariate Plots of (a) Na-normalized Ca^{2+} versus Mg^{2+} (b) Na-normalized Ca^{2+} versus HCO_3^- .

Additionally, the scatter plot (Figure 4c) shows that the ratio of this tendency is -0.32, and the correlation coefficient is 0.52, indicating that most of the samples are linear with the -1- slope line. It suggests that groundwater composition may also be affected by ion exchange.

2.5 Geochemical Modeling

2.5.1 Saturation Index

The saturation index is a standard method for assessing water's equilibrium with minerals (Amiri, Sohrabi, & Dadgar, 2015). PHREEQC has been used to determine the saturation indices for Halite, fluorite, gypsum, calcite, and dolomite. Groundwater in recharge zones or up-gradient parts of a regional flow system is generally unsaturated in fluorite calcite, gypsum, and dolomite due to a lack of interaction with the aquifer surface or inadequate mineral sources. Multiple water-rock interactions will occur as groundwater flows to the runoff zone and ultimately to the affluent area, and groundwater may attain equilibrium with these minerals. As a result of increasing mineral decomposition, TDS in groundwater would rise along the flow

path (Li & Hui Qian, 2014). As a result, the SI vs TDS plot is quite helpful in analyzing the evolution of groundwater along the flow channel.

The Saturation Index plot (Figure 7) in the current study reveals that the weak connection of TDS with calcite, dolomite, and fluorite predicts the oversaturation of these minerals. On the other hand, Halite and gypsum exhibited a positive correlation with TDS, and 99% of the Halite and approximately 30% of the gypsum samples lie below the zero line, implying dissolution of halite mineral and gypsum along the flow direction and elevated TDS concentration. Furthermore, gypsum and dolomite precipitation has been shown to have less of an effect on carbonate weathering in the groundwater in our study area (Figure 4b).

Fig. 7 Mineral saturation indices in groundwater samples (Halite, calcite, dolomite, gypsum, and fluoride).

2.5.2 Ion Exchange

The chemical constituents of groundwater change as it travels through its flow path. It is measured by the Chloro-Alkaline Indices (CAI). To interpret the ionization between groundwater and the surrounding environment, Schoeller suggested two chloro-alkaline indices, CAI 1 and CAI 2. Na^+ and K^+ are exchanged with Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} from the rocks (direct ion-exchange process); if the Chloro-Alkaline Indices are positive, Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} are exchanged with the rocks from the water, negative indices occur (Schoeller, 1965). CAI-1 values in our study area ranged from 17.3 to 50.7, with a median of 2.5, while CAI-2 values ranged from 0.03 to 809.5, with a mean of 25.1. It was observed that 45 samples from the CAI-1 group exhibited negative CAI values, signifying a reverse ion exchange process; however, in the CAI-2 group, all CAI values were positive, implying that Na^+ and K^+ from the water are exchanged with Mg^+ and Ca^+ from a direct ion-exchange process. The chloro-alkaline indices revealed that direct ions and reverse ion-exchange processes were involved in the evolution of Hydrochemistry in the research area's groundwater.

2.6 Groundwater Quality Analysis for Drinking Water

2.6.1 Assessment of Water Quality Index (WQI)

Implementation of water quality monitoring and analysis results is the focus of the WQI. Each sample's specific water quality index was computed per WHO guidelines to determine the general appropriateness of groundwater for ingestion (WHO, 2011). The Water Quality Index (WQI) has been used to categorize water quality into distinct categories. Generally, excellent water quality is defined as a WQI value of 0- 25, 26-50 defined as good, 51-75 poor, 76-100 very poor, and > 100 defined as unfit for ingestion (Brown et al., 1972; Ram et al., 2021). According to the findings of the WQI, 13% of the groundwater samples were good, 28% poor, 39% very poor, and 38% were unfit for human consumption (see Tables 3 to 5).

Table 3 Relative weight for each parameter

Chemical Parameters	S_n	$1/S_n$	$\sum 1/S_n$	$K=1/\sum 1/S_n$	$W_n=K/S_n$	Ideal value (V_i)	Mean value (V_n)	V_n/S_n	$V_n/S_n*100=Q_n$	W_nQ_n	WQI
pH	8.5	0.12	11.82	0.0846	0.00995	7	7.5	0.33	33	0.328	117.03
EC (μ S)	1000	0.00	11.82	0.0846	0.00008	0	1490	1.49	149.0	0.013	
TDS (mg/L)	1000	0.00	11.82	0.0846	0.00008	0	894	0.894	89.4	0.008	
Hardness (mg/L)	500	0.00	11.82	0.0846	0.00017	0	392.5	0.785	78.5	0.013	
HCO ₃ ⁻ (mg/L)	300	0.00	11.82	0.0846	0.00028	0	325	1.083333	108.3	0.031	
Ca ²⁺ (mg/L)	75	0.01	11.82	0.0846	0.00113	0	56	0.746667	74.7	0.084	
F ⁻ (mg/L)	1.5	0.67	11.82	0.0846	0.05641	0	0.425	0.283333	28.3	1.598	
Mg ²⁺ (mg/L)	150	0.01	11.82	0.0846	0.00056	0	61.5	0.41	41.0	0.023	
Na ⁺ (mg/L)	200	0.01	11.82	0.0846	0.00042	0	15.5	0.0775	7.8	0.003	
K ⁺ (mg/L)	200	0.01	11.82	0.0846	0.00042	0	1.9	0.0095	1.0	0.000	
Cl ⁻ (mg/L)	250	0.00	11.82	0.0846	0.00034	0	112.5	0.45	45.0	0.015	
NO ₃ (N)	45	0.02	11.82	0.0846	0.00188	0	40.5	0.9	90.0	0.169	
PO ₄ (mg/L)	0.1	10.00	11.82	0.0846	0.84613	0	0.135	1.35	135.0	114.227	
SO ₄ ²⁻ (mg/L)	250	0.00	11.82	0.0846	0.00034	0	95.5	0.382	38.2	0.013	
Fe (mg/L)	1.5	0.67	11.82	0.0846	0.05641	0	0.115	0.076667	7.7	0.432	
As (ppb)	10	0.10	11.82	0.0846	0.00846	0	0.115	0.0115	1.2	0.010	
Turbidity(NTU)	5	0.20	11.82	0.0846	0.01692	0	0.195	0.039	3.9	0.066	
		11.82			1					117.035	

Table 4 Categorization of water quality based on WQI.

Category	WQI	Water quality	Water Sample
A	0-25	Excellent	0%
B	25-50	Good	13%
C	51-75	Poor	28%
D	76-100	Very poor	39.00%
E	> 100	Not suitable	38.00%

Table 5 WQI value at single sampling locations.

Samples	WQI values	Water quality	Samples	WQI	Water quality
1	80.50116653	Poor	62	95.44932211	Very poor
2	16.36791317	Good	63	112.2414899	Not suitable
3	97.88059031	Very Poor	64	121.1452735	Not suitable
4	116.2841404	Not suitable	65	112.6868691	Not suitable
5	130.6364497	Not suitable	66	87.13780494	Very poor
6	130.7501863	Not suitable	67	81.10984811	Very poor
7	89.3392811	Very Poor	68	114.9946182	Not suitable
8	765.8191659	Not suitable	69	89.37811976	Very poor
9	89.25039672	Poor	70	95.8461742	Very poor
10	122.3641774	Not suitable	71	53.91239385	Poor
11	146.7494349	Not suitable	72	80.62308087	Very poor
12	87.44891657	Very poor	73	81.31084271	Very poor
13	97.81786288	Very poor	74	115.6010758	Not suitable
14	80.00691252	Very poor	75	188.0584459	Not suitable
15	49.07428147	Poor	76	114.4424571	Not suitable
16	70.63132039	Very poor	77	148.9326076	Not suitable
17	47.57790836	Good	78	130.1033913	Not suitable
18	44.66977624	Good	79	83.57307064	Very poor
19	47.68760546	Good	80	98.68590422	Very poor
20	36.3310543	Good	81	72.63194767	Very poor
21	38.3738446	Good	82	89.07162602	Very poor
22	48.15106048	Good	83	116.0821195	Not suitable
23	80.3788349	Very poor	84	146.2175969	Not suitable
24	89.49006256	Very poor	85	62.81312625	Poor
25	80.22359024	Very poor	86	99.11468301	Very poor
26	63.51888945	Poor	87	148.8136974	Not suitable
27	61.49642479	Poor	88	116.6213574	Not suitable
28	86.86438827	Very poor	89	82.31088003	Very poor
29	273.0294819	Not suitable	90	90.59343272	Very poor
30	78.66502101	Very poor	91	99.62442456	Very Poor
31	307.2728862	Not suitable	92	115.4533503	Not suitable
32	53.69319876	Poor	93	150.165317	Not suitable
33	80.08653931	Very poor	94	131.6599813	Not suitable
34	113.4364632	Not suitable	95	134.279048	Not suitable
35	43.36688021	Good	96	65.33483966	Poor
36	66.15957554	Poor	97	96.75217647	Very poor
37	116.6044679	Not suitable	98	122.54732	Not suitable
38	83.6968657	Very poor	99	105.0503844	Not suitable
39	63.72177668	Poor	100	83.22078731	Very poor
40	39.13920565	Good	101	81.69232415	Very poor
41	45.07659875	Good	102	34.42852861	Good
42	77.5072127	Very poor	103	65.6568774	Poor
43	53.70045994	Poor	104	49.1006489	Good
44	64.76985269	Poor	105	53.96405523	Poor

45	88.61095358	Very poor	106	37.34226072	Good
46	113.8752958	Not suitable	107	113.9850108	Not suitable
47	131.3593721	Not suitable	108	128.6061673	Not suitable
48	78.52421521	Very poor	109	53.46084786	Poor
49	112.3388504	Not suitable	110	38.38606625	Good
50	112.6806277	Not suitable	111	19.45956174	Excellent
51	61.39720797	poor water	112	28.8361902	Good
52	121.6028433	Not suitable	113	62.33539734	Poor
53	62.37716609	poor water	114	62.25842562	Poor
54	79.67464396	Very poor	115	53.40751033	Poor
55	113.0691328	Not suitable	116	36.23468178	Good
56	86.38928538	Very poor	117	61.81557691	Poor
57	68.51519332	Poor	118	63.17007148	Poor
58	60.37247456	Poor	119	54.92920891	Poor
59	107.2455044	Not suitable	120	47.27290371	Good
60	89.84008678	Very Poor	121	61.14216893	Poor
61	86.97276825	Very Poor	122	95.85169057	Very poor
			123	61.72187378	Poor

2.7 Groundwater analysis for Irrigation Purpose

Groundwater's appropriateness for agricultural use is influenced by its chemical components. The permeability index (PI), sodium absorption ratio (SAR), Kelly ratio (KR), and sodium percentage Na% were performed to identify the irrigation quality of groundwater. Groundwater is categorized based on calculated parameters (Table 6). SAR is a helpful technique for interpreting the adequacy of groundwater for agriculture. The sodium level in water is an essential indicator because when sodium interacts with soil, it decreases the soil's permeability. Salt inhibits osmotic action, preventing water from entering the plant's leaves and stems and reducing growth (Marghade, Malpe, & Zade, 2011).

Table 6 Statistical analysis of irrigation water quality parameters of groundwater samples

Parameters	Max	Min	Mean
SAR	26.99	0.89	5.44
Na%	93.2	21.94	62.18
KR	13.69	0.27	2.39
PI	463.95	24.36	109.83

Irrigation water quality is classified into several categories.

Parameters	Categories	Ranges	No of samples
SAR	Excellent	0-10	120
	Good	10--18	2
	Fair	18-26	1
	poor	>26	
Na%	Excellent	0-20	0
	Good	20-40	13

	permissible	40-60	33
	Unsure	60-80	58
	Unsuitable	>80	19
KR	Suitable	<1	30
	Unsuitable	>1	93
PI	Grade first	>75	74
	Grade 2nd	25-75	48
	Grade 3rd	<25	1

SAR is classified into various groups. SAR values of 0–10 are considered excellent for irrigation, and values within 10–18 are considered suitable for irrigation with less sodium hazard content. SAR with a level above 26 is deemed inappropriate for irrigation because of the high sodium concentration. The maximum and minimum SAR values are 0.89 and 26.99, with a median of 5.44. The USSS diagram explains that many samples come in the C1S1 and C2S2 categories (Figure 8); they might be used for irrigation without causing too much Na^+ conversion.

Fig.8 Classification of irrigation water using USSS diagram (USSS, 1954)

Sodium percentage ($\text{Na} \%$) is a significant indicator of the sodium threat in irrigation water. Irrigation water with high sodium levels decreases soil permeability, which impacts plant headway, so it is a powerful indicator for evaluating groundwater on an agronomic scale (Amiri et al., 2015). Wilcox (Richards, 1954) proposed the Wilcox diagram for determining the quality of irrigation water. The $\text{Na} \%$ was obtained using this technique, and the findings revealed that 36% of groundwater samples are excellent to acceptable, 26%

are within the permissible range, 47% are doubtful, and 15% are inappropriate for irrigation. (Table 6 & Figure 9).

Fig.9 Groundwater classification based on sodium and EC concentrations (Wilcox, 1954)

Kelly index or KR is another significant parameter to evaluate the subsurface water condition for agriculture in terms of sodium contents suggested by (Kelley, 1963). The Kelly index divides water into acceptable, moderately suitable, and unsuitable for agriculture. KR is appropriate for irrigation if it is less than 1, relatively good if it is between 1 and 2, and unacceptable if greater than 2 (Srinivasamoorthy, Gopinath, Chidambaram, Vasanthavigar, & Sarma, 2014). Based on KR results, 30 water samples came within the suitable, 29 samples are moderately appropriate, whereas 64 samples are inappropriate for agriculture activities (Table 6).

The Permeability index was employed to examine the soil's permeability because long-term irrigation water use affects the soil quality, and ions like bicarbonate, sodium, calcium, and magnesium in water affect the permeability of the soil (Raghunath, 1987). Doneen categorized irrigation water into three groups based on its permeability index: I, II, and III (Doneen, 1964). If the PI value is greater than 75, the water is regarded to be in the first group; if the PI value is between 25 and 75, it is considered to be in the second group; and if the PI value is less than 25, the water is deemed to be unfit for irrigation. According to Table.5, 60.16 % of samples fall into the first class, 39% fall into the second class, and only one groundwater sample has a value of less than 25. As a result, all water samples are appropriate for irrigation except for one.

Conclusion

To conclude the present study, various statistical analyses, graphical tools, and hydrochemical modelling were applied to understand hydrochemistry, its development, and its suitability for human consumption and agricultural uses in the designated research area. The groundwater's pH indicated that the water was slightly alkaline. Analysis showed the concentrations of dominant cations is in this sequence: $\text{Na}^+ > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{K}^+$, whereas, dominant of anions is in this sequence: $\text{HCO}_3^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-}$. The Piper plot exhibited that most water samples belong to the Calcium type, no dominant type, and Chloride water type. Furthermore, Gibb's diagram demonstrated that rock dominance and precipitation are the primary controlling processes governing groundwater chemistry. According to our findings, high salinity is the most significant source of groundwater pollution in the study area. The positive correlation between TDS, Na^+ , Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , and NO_3^- indicates that these parameters are the principal contributors to groundwater salinity.

Furthermore, the chloro-alkaline indices predicted that apart from halite dissolution, the presence of reverse cation exchange would increase the concentration of sodium ions (Na^+) released from the minerals into groundwater. WQI values revealed that 85% of groundwater samples in the research area are poor for human consumption. In addition, the salinity concentration of groundwater determines its Excellency for agriculture. Na% and KR revealed that 64% of the water samples were not appropriate for farming due to high salinity.

It is suggested that areas with poor groundwater quality for human consumption should be filtered regularly. Appropriate soil supplements should be provided to agricultural fields where groundwater quality is poor for irrigation. More attention needs to be paid to groundwater salinity fluctuations to maintain long-term use in future management.

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References

1. Ansa-Asare O, Darko H, Asante K. Groundwater quality assessment of Akatsi, Adidome and Ho districts in the Volta Region of Ghana. *Desalination*. 2009;248(1-3):446-52.
2. Walton WC. Groundwater resource evaluation. McGraw-Hill series in water resources and environmental engineering (USA) eng. 1970.
3. Prasanth SS, Magesh N, Jitheshlal K, Chandrasekar N, Gangadhar K. Evaluation of groundwater quality and its suitability for drinking and agricultural use in the coastal stretch of Alappuzha District, Kerala, India. *Applied Water Science*. 2012;2(3):165-75.
4. Reddy BM, Sunitha V, Prasad M, Reddy YS, Reddy MR. Evaluation of groundwater suitability for domestic and agricultural utility in semi-arid region of Anantapur, Andhra Pradesh State, South India. *Groundwater for Sustainable Development*. 2019;9:100262.
5. Raju NJ, Shukla U, Ram P. Hydrogeochemistry for the assessment of groundwater quality in Varanasi: a fast-urbanizing center in Uttar Pradesh, India. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*. 2011;173(1):279-300.

6. Abbas Z, Mapoma HWT, Su C, Aziz SZ, Ma Y, Abbas N. Spatial analysis of groundwater suitability for drinking and irrigation in Lahore, Pakistan. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*. 2018;190(7):1-16.
7. Asia DS. water vision 2025, Country Report, Pakistan. Maharashtra, India, Global Water Partnership. South Asia Technical Advisory Committee Regional Office. 2000.
8. Siyal ZA, Ahmed A, Samo KA, Samo IA, Pathan E. Assessment of the Quality of Groundwater for Drinking Purpose in Rajanpur Tehsil, Pakistan. *Quaid-E-Awam University Research Journal of Engineering, Science & Technology, Nawabshah*. 2020;18(2):50-7.
9. Raza M, Hussain F, Lee J-Y, Shakoor MB, Kwon KD. Groundwater status in Pakistan: A review of contamination, health risks, and potential needs. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*. 2017;47(18):1713-62.
10. STATISTICS FBO. Government of Pakistan. Change. 2007.
11. Afzal M, Yaseen M, Mahmood S, Khan M. Estimation of potential rainfall recharge in the pothwar area. *University of Engineering and Technology Taxila Technical Journal*. 2015;20(2):85.
12. Tahir MA, Rasheed H. Distribution of nitrate in the water resources of Pakistan. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*. 2008;2(11):397-403.
13. Siddiqui S, Safi MWA, Tariq A, Rehman NU, Haider SW. GIS Based Universal Soil Erosion Estimation in District Chakwal Punjab, Pakistan. *International Journal of Economic and Environmental Geology*. 2020;11(2):30-6.
14. Ghani MW, Arshad M, Shabbir A, Mehmood N, Ahmad I. Investigation of potential water harvesting sites at Potohar using modeling approach. *Pakistan Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. 2013;50(4).
15. Balouch S, Rais M, Hussain I, Akram A. Squamate diversity in different croplands of district Chakwal, Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of King Saud University-Science*. 2016;28(3):255-60.
16. Moyo A. Assessment of the effect of soil erosion on nutrient loss from granite-derived sandy soils under different tillage systems in Zimbabwe: Ph. D. Thesis, University of Zimbabwe, Harare, Zimbabwe; 2003.
17. Baker DM, Lillie RJ, Yeats RS, Johnson GD, Yousuf M, Zamin ASH. Development of the Himalayan frontal thrust zone: Salt Range, Pakistan. *Geology*. 1988;16(1):3-7.
18. Elahi M, Martin N. The physiography of the Potwar, West Pakistan. *Geol Bull Panjab Univ*. 1961;1:5-14.
19. Wynne A. I.—On the Connexion between Travelled Blocks in the Upper Punjab and a supposed Glacial Period in Upper India. *Geological Magazine*. 1881;8(3):97-9.
20. Association APH, Association AWW, Federation WPC, Federation WE. Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater: American Public Health Association.; 1912.
21. Ndoye S, Fontaine C, Gaye CB, Razack M. Groundwater quality and suitability for different uses in the Saloum area of Senegal. *Water*. 2018;10(12):1837.
22. Parkhurst DL, Appelo C. User's guide to PHREEQC (Version 2): A computer program for speciation, batch-reaction, one-dimensional transport, and inverse geochemical calculations. *Water-resources investigations report*. 1999;99(4259):312.
23. Brown RM, McClelland NI, Deininger RA, O'Connor MF. A water quality index—crashing the psychological barrier. *Indicators of environmental quality: Springer*; 1972. p. 173-82.
24. Wilcox L. Classification and use of irrigation waters: US Department of Agriculture; 1955.
25. Staff USL. Diagnosis and improvement of saline and alkali soils. *USDA Agric Handb 60*. 1954.
26. Rao NS. Seasonal variation of groundwater quality in a part of Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Environmental Geology*. 2006;49(3):413-29.
27. Jamali MZ, Solangi GS, Keerio MA. Assessment of Groundwater Quality of Taluka Larkana, Sindh, Pakistan. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*. 2020;11(5,May-2020).
28. Chen J, Huang Q, Lin Y, Fang Y, Qian H, Liu R, et al. Hydrogeochemical characteristics and quality assessment of groundwater in an irrigated region, Northwest China. *Water*. 2019;11(1):96.
29. Adelekan B, Ogunde O. Quality of water from dug wells and the lagoon in Lagos Nigeria and associated health risks. *Scientific Research and Essays*. 2012;7(11):1195-211.
30. Kim K-H, Susaya JP, Park CG, Uhm J-H, Hur J. Comprehensive monitoring of drinking well water quality in Seoul metropolitan city, Korea. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*. 2013;185(8):6353-78.
31. WHO., Organization WH, Staff WHO. Guidelines for drinking-water quality: World health organization; 2004.
32. Qureshi A, Lashari B, Kori S, Lashari G, editors. Hydro-salinity behavior of shallow groundwater aquifer underlain by salty groundwater in Sindh Pakistan. *Proceedings, Fifteenth International Water Technology Conference*; 2011.

33. Van Weert F, Van der Gun J, Reckman J. Global overview of saline groundwater occurrence and genesis. International Groundwater Resources Assessment Centre. 2009.
34. Wu J, Wang L, Wang S, Tian R, Xue C, Feng W, et al. Spatiotemporal variation of groundwater quality in an arid area experiencing long-term paper wastewater irrigation, northwest China. *Environmental Earth Sciences*. 2017;76(13):1-14.
35. Mostafa MG, Uddin SH, Haque A. Assessment of hydro-geochemistry and groundwater quality of Rajshahi City in Bangladesh. *Applied Water Science*. 2017;7(8):4663-71.
36. Chen J, Qian H, Wu H, Gao Y, Li X. Assessment of arsenic and fluoride pollution in groundwater in Dawukou area, Northwest China, and the associated health risk for inhabitants. *Environmental Earth Sciences*. 2017;76(8):314.
37. Mostaza-Colado D, Carreño-Conde F, Rasines-Ladero R, Iepure S. Hydrogeochemical characterization of a shallow alluvial aquifer: 1 baseline for groundwater quality assessment and resource management. *Science of the Total Environment*. 2018;639:1110-25.
38. Karthikeyan B, Rajendran R, Ramasamy M, Lakshmanan E. Nitrate pollution in shallow groundwater of a hard rock region in South Central India. *J Environ Science & Engg Vol*. 2012;54(1):64-70.
39. Piper AM. A graphic procedure in the geochemical interpretation of water-analyses. *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union*. 1944;25(6):914-28.
40. Ganyaglo SY, Banoeng-Yakubo B, Osae S, Dampare SB, Fianko JR, Bhuiyan MA. Hydrochemical and isotopic characterization of groundwaters in the eastern region of Ghana. *Journal of Water Resource and Protection*. 2010;2(3):199.
41. Bhatia H. A textbook on environmental pollution and control. GalgotiaPublication Pvt Ltd, New Delhi. 2003.
42. Gibbs RJ. Mechanisms controlling world water chemistry. *Science*. 1970;170(3962):1088-90.
43. Mattos JB, Cruz MJM, De Paula FCF, Sales EF. Spatio-seasonal changes in the hydrogeochemistry of groundwaters in a highland tropical zone. *Journal of South American Earth Sciences*. 2018;88:275-86.
44. Vickers NJ. Animal communication: when i'm calling you, will you answer too? *Current biology*. 2017;27(14):R713-R5.
45. Nagaraju A, Thejaswi A, Sreedhar Y. Assessment of Groundwater Quality of Udayagiri area, Nellore District, Andhra Pradesh, South India Using Multivariate Statistical Techniques. *Earth Sciences Research Journal*. 2016;20(4):E1-E7.
46. Subramani T, Rajmohan N, Elango L. Groundwater geochemistry and identification of hydrogeochemical processes in a hard rock region, Southern India. *Environmental monitoring and assessment*. 2010;162(1):123-37.
47. Saravanan K, Srinivasamoorthy K, Gopinath S, Prakash R, Suma C. Investigation of hydrogeochemical processes and groundwater quality in Upper Vellar sub-basin Tamilnadu, India. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*. 2016;9(5):372.
48. Feng F, Jia Y, Yang Y, Huan H, Lian X, Xu X, et al. Hydrogeochemical and statistical analysis of high fluoride groundwater in northern China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*. 2020:1-22.
49. Kumar M, Ramanathan A, Rao MS, Kumar B. Identification and evaluation of hydrogeochemical processes in the groundwater environment of Delhi, India. *Environmental geology*. 2006;50(7):1025-39.
50. Stallard R, Edmond J. Geochemistry of the Amazon: 2. The influence of geology and weathering environment on the dissolved load. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*. 1983;88(C14):9671-88.
51. Sonkamble S, Sahya A, Mondal N, Harikumar P. Appraisal and evolution of hydrochemical processes from proximity basalt and granite areas of Deccan Volcanic Province (DVP) in India. *Journal of Hydrology*. 2012;438:181-93.
52. Mukherjee A, Fryar AE. Deeper groundwater chemistry and geochemical modeling of the arsenic affected western Bengal basin, West Bengal, India. *Applied Geochemistry*. 2008;23(4):863-94.
53. Ettazarini S. Processes of water-rock interaction in the Turonian aquifer of Oum Er-Rabia Basin, Morocco. *Environmental Geology*. 2005;49(2):293-9.
54. Amiri V, Sohrabi N, Dadgar MA. Evaluation of groundwater chemistry and its suitability for drinking and agricultural uses in the Lenjanat plain, central Iran. *Environmental Earth Sciences*. 2015;74(7):6163-76.
55. Li P, Hui Qian JW. Hydrogeochemistry and quality assessment of shallow groundwater in the southern part of the Yellow River alluvial plain (Zhongwei section), Northwest China. *Earth Sciences Research Journal*. 2014;18(1):27-38.
56. Schoeller H. Qualitative evaluation of groundwater resources. *Methods and techniques of groundwater investigations and development UNESCO*. 1965;5483.
57. WHO G. Guidelines for drinking-water quality. World Health Organization. 2011;216:303-4.

58. Ram A, Tiwari S, Pandey H, Chaurasia AK, Singh S, Singh Y. Groundwater quality assessment using water quality index (WQI) under GIS framework. *Applied Water Science*. 2021;11(2):1-20.
59. Marghade D, Malpe D, Zade A. Geochemical characterization of groundwater from northeastern part of Nagpur urban, Central India. *Environmental Earth Sciences*. 2011;62(7):1419-30.
60. Richards L. *Diagnosis and Improvement of Saline and Alkali Soils Handbook*. 1954;60.
61. Kelley W. Use of saline irrigation water. *Soil science*. 1963;95(6):385-91.
62. Srinivasamoorthy K, Gopinath M, Chidambaram S, Vasanthavigar M, Sarma V. Hydrochemical characterization and quality appraisal of groundwater from Pungar sub basin, Tamilnadu, India. *Journal of King Saud University-Science*. 2014;26(1):37-52.
63. Raghunath HM. *Ground water: hydrogeology, ground water survey and pumping tests, rural water supply and irrigation systems*: New Age International; 1987.
64. Doneen LD. *Notes on water quality in agriculture*: Department of Water Science and Engineering, University of California, Davis; 1964.

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